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A NON-STANDARD LEARNING PARADIGM: THE EXPLORATORY-RESEARCH MODEL OF LEARNING

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Abstract: *This article explores the application of a research-based learning model in the educational process. This model, coupled with innovative pedagogical technologies, is considered within the context of the development of professionalization in education. The relevance of this topic stems from the fact that one of the key objectives of modernizing the educational system, taking into account the needs of modern society for a new generation of engineers, is the training of highly qualified technical specialists. The research-based model of teaching professional Russian to students at non-linguistic universities is defined as a means of developing the linguistic and professional competence of future technical specialists. It is concluded that through active research and exploration, students develop productive critical and creative thinking, which is necessary for adapting to the rapidly changing modern world.*

Keywords: *research and exploration model, innovative technologies, critical thinking, activity.*

1. One of the key objectives of the reform and reorganization of higher education institutions as part of the modernization of the education system, taking into account the needs of modern society for a new generation of engineers, is the training of highly qualified technical specialists. Improving the professional focus of training requires consideration of educational development trends, the relevance of the education received to current socioeconomic conditions, and consideration of future changes in these conditions. High-quality training entails not only the development of specific theoretical knowledge, skills, and professional abilities, but also the development of professional qualities and attributes, and the development of an intellectual, comprehensively developed, and creative individual. While intellectual potential represents a person's ability to function adequately in a specific social environment, creative potential serves as a prerequisite for self-development [1].

2. In this context, great importance is attached to innovative pedagogical technologies and modern active and interactive methods within the framework of the development of professionalization of education. These technologies and methods represent fundamentally new ways and means of interaction between teachers and learners, ensuring the effective achievement of pedagogical results. We fully agree with the opinion of M.I. Korsakov, who asserts that interactive learning is based on the learners' own experience, their direct interaction with the area of experience being mastered [2]. In other words, the language material must be related to the students' future professional activities, and the topics and situations must be consistent with their professional focus. Therefore, teachers of professional Russian at non-linguistic universities must pay close attention to developing the linguistic and professional competence of future specialists.

It should be noted that the issues of moving away from the information-reproductive method of teaching to the use of innovative technologies for the purpose of developing professional competencies are addressed in the works of G.M. Andreev, V.P. Bepalko, V.A. Slastenin, E.S. Polat, N.I. Almazov, N.F. Koryakovtsev, L.V. Yarotskaya and others. In their opinion, the new non-standard paradigm of teaching instead of the traditional explanatory-illustrative one contributes to the creation of subject-subject relations instead of manipulative subject-object ones. According to the concept of V.A. Slastenin, it is possible to identify a set of criteria for pedagogical innovations: novelty, optimality, high efficiency, the possibility of creative application of innovation in mass experience [3].

Interactive learning is focused on developing and nurturing students' abilities and skills to structure and adjust their learning and cognitive processes, including mastering the metalanguage of their specialty. Subject-to-subject relationships within the framework of innovative technologies facilitate the development of critical and creative thinking, cognitive skills, and strategies in each participant in the educational process. As M.Sh. Ruzmetova notes, «The main thing is to be able to acquire knowledge not passively, but actively—that is, by making an effort—and to be able to use this knowledge in everyday life, both within and outside of education» [4, pp. 100-101]. In this context, the teacher's task as a mentor is to present a problem-based presentation of the educational material. The goal is to develop and foster research activity. This postulate is based on the fact that, as a result of research into problematic issues, tasks, and situations, «the development of a special style of mental activity, research activity, and independence of students is one of the important goals of problem-based learning» [5].

In the process of professionally-oriented training, the use of interactive methods such as discussions, press conferences, role-playing and business games, and the method of concrete situations not only contributes to the intensification and optimization of the entire educational process, but also promotes the development of students' thinking skills, which are necessary not only for their studies, but also for their future professional activities. It should be noted that by intensification of the educational process, we, following Azimov E.G. and Shchukin A.N., understand "a set of the most rational methods of scientific organization of work, ensuring the achievement of the set educational goal in a minimum time with the least expenditure of effort and resources" [6, 350]. The development of thinking skills and the search and research activities of students is facilitated, in particular, by problem-based assignments, the so-called Socratic or heuristic questions.

According to L.L. Tkacheva, "Socratic questions lead to the development of critical and creative thinking, stimulate the development of active cognitive activity in students, develop the ability to think differently, allow students to have and defend their own opinions and positions, and allow them to argue with the teacher. To develop such students, it is necessary to create special conditions and use innovative methodological tools" [7, p. 92].

As follows from the above, the use of innovative teaching tools helps develop skills and abilities in research and exploration. Through searching, research, and generalization, students learn to make informed decisions, analyze various aspects of phenomena and processes, and argue and defend their point of view.

Let's consider the use of the research and exploration method in professional Russian classes, aimed at developing the competency-based skills of future technical specialists, specifically the method of analyzing a specific situation and learning task.

Situation 1. You are participating in an experiment measuring buoyant force in water. Of the metals offered, lead and sodium, sodium has been selected. You observe how a piece of sodium, a soft silvery metal, is immersed in water. The sodium does not sink in the water; instead, it steadily decreases in size as a result of the violent reaction. It floats and ripples across the water, emitting sparks of fire. The experiment culminates in a sharp explosion, and the sodium disappears.

Your task is to determine where the metallic sodium disappeared to. What new substance did the original material - metallic sodium - transform into when it reacted with water? What phenomenon or process did you witness: a physical or chemical transformation? Suggest your hypothesis. Provide

the formula of the new substance into which sodium is transformed as a result of the chemical reaction (caustic alkali NaOH). Are your conclusions consistent with the law of conservation of energy? Justify your answer.

Suggest and describe your version of an experiment involving a physical (melting, electrical conductivity) rather than chemical transformation of metallic sodium, in which the starting material remains the same - the same substance, sodium metal.

Construct your answer in the form of a proof-based argument. When answering, use objective, conditional, and cause-and-effect syntactic constructions in the evidentiary part.

Use introductory words: in my opinion, so, thus, from the point of view of..., according to theory..., according to the law..., etc.

Educational ecological task: «Think and Answer!»

Why did they refuse to use salt to clear ice from streets in winter, despite the fact that the ice melted even at very low temperatures? Describe the reaction that occurred in the above situation. Point out the advantages (the benefit of saving labor on snow removal) and disadvantages (risks: corrosion of metal parts of cars, damage to trees, pollution of rivers and drains, etc.) of this use of natural laws for human needs. Suggest your alternative solution to this environmental problem. In your answer, use informational and evaluative intent, introductory words indicating the source of the message, and a consistent flow of thoughts.

Thus, the research-based learning model promotes the development of productive critical and creative thinking, an analytical mindset, and the linguistic and professional competencies of future specialists.

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